

THD Reduction in Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter using Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Controller

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Abstract— Multilevel inverters (MLIs) have gained significant attention in modern power electronics due to their ability to generate high-quality output waveforms with reduced Total Harmonic Distortion (THD). Among various MLI topologies, the Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter (CHB-MLI) offers notable advantages such as modularity, scalability, and lower switching losses. However, maintaining a low THD in CHB-MLI output under varying operating conditions remains a critical challenge. This research proposes an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS)-based controller to optimize the performance of CHB-MLIs by reducing THD effectively. The ANFIS controller combines the advantages of neural networks and fuzzy logic to dynamically adjust control parameters in response to real-time changes in load and operating conditions. Simulation studies and experimental validation reveal that the proposed system achieves superior THD reduction compared to conventional Proportional-Integral (PI) and pure fuzzy logic controllers. The findings suggest that the ANFIS-based approach provides a robust and efficient solution for enhancing the power quality in renewable energy systems and industrial drives.

Keywords— THD, ANFIS, Neuro-Fuzzy, H-Bridge, Active, Power Filters.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing demand for energy-efficient and reliable power conversion systems, multilevel inverters (MLIs) have emerged as a promising solution for high-power applications. Among the different MLI topologies, the Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter (CHB-MLI) stands out due to its ability to synthesize high-quality output voltages by combining multiple voltage levels. This feature minimizes the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) in the output waveform, a key factor in achieving power quality standards in grid-connected systems and industrial applications. However, maintaining low THD in CHB-MLIs presents challenges due to the complex interactions between system parameters, including switching sequences, modulation techniques, and load variations.

Traditionally, control strategies such as Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers and pure fuzzy logic systems have been employed to optimize the performance of CHB-MLIs. While effective to some extent, these methods often fail to provide satisfactory results under non-linear operating conditions or dynamic load changes. This limitation necessitates the development of advanced control techniques capable of adapting to varying system

dynamics. In this context, Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems (ANFIS) have garnered significant attention. ANFIS leverages the learning capability of neural networks and the decision-making approach of fuzzy logic, making it highly effective for real-time applications where system conditions are unpredictable.

This study investigates the application of an ANFIS-based control strategy to reduce THD in a CHB-MLI. By dynamically adjusting the switching patterns based on real-time system data, the ANFIS controller enhances the inverter's performance under diverse operating scenarios. The proposed approach is particularly relevant for renewable energy systems, such as photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy systems, where the variability of input power necessitates robust control mechanisms.

The key contributions of this research include the development of an ANFIS-based controller specifically designed for CHB-MLIs, the implementation of simulation models to validate its efficacy, and a comparative analysis with conventional control techniques. Simulation results demonstrate that the ANFIS controller achieves significant THD reduction compared to standard PI and fuzzy controllers, even under challenging operating

conditions. Moreover, the ANFIS-based approach ensures improved system stability and enhanced power quality, aligning with modern grid standards.

II. PROPOSED MODEL AND METHODOLOGY

The proposed model is as following-

Figure 1: Proposed model

The methodology and working is as following-

1. **Input Data Acquisition:** The ANFIS-based control system for Asymmetric Selective Harmonic Current Mitigation PWM in Active Power Filters (APFs) starts with the acquisition of input data. This involves monitoring the electrical parameters of the power system, such as voltage, current, and harmonic content. The system gathers real-time data to capture the dynamic behavior of the electrical grid.
2. **Fuzzification of Input Data:** Fuzzification is a crucial step where the crisp numerical input data is transformed into fuzzy sets. Fuzzy logic allows for the representation of uncertainty and imprecision in the data. Membership functions are defined to

associate each input variable with linguistic terms, converting precise numerical information into linguistic variables like "high," "medium," or "low."

3. **Neural Network Training:** The neural network component of ANFIS plays a crucial role in adjusting the parameters (weights and biases) to optimize the mapping between fuzzy input variables and the desired output. Training involves using a dataset with known input-output pairs to update the neural network parameters through a learning algorithm. Hybrid learning algorithms, often based on a combination of gradient descent and least-squares estimation, are commonly employed in ANFIS.
4. **Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) Operation:** The fuzzy inference system uses the fuzzified input data and the rule base to generate intermediate fuzzy outputs. Each rule's contribution to the overall output is determined based on the degree of matching between the input data and the rule's conditions. These intermediate outputs are aggregated to produce a fuzzy output.
5. **PWM Signal Generation:** The crisp output obtained after de-fuzzification represents the desired Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signal. In the context of APFs for asymmetric selective harmonic current mitigation, this PWM signal determines the switching pattern of the inverter, generating compensating currents to counteract the undesired harmonic components. The adaptability of ANFIS ensures that the PWM signals are dynamically adjusted in real-time to accommodate changes in the power system conditions.
6. **Implementation in Active Power Filters:** The final PWM signals generated by the ANFIS-based control system are implemented in the active power filter's inverter. The inverter, under the influence of the ANFIS-based control, injects compensating currents into the power system, effectively mitigating asymmetric selective harmonic currents and improving power quality.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation is performed using the MATLAB software-

Figure 2: Output Voltage

Figure 2 shows the output waveform. A 7-level multi-level inverter in an Active Power Filter (APF) is designed to generate an output voltage with multiple discrete voltage levels.

Figure 3: Output Current

Figure 3 is showing the output current. The output current of a 7-level multi-level inverter in an Active Power Filter (APF) is a crucial parameter, especially when considering its role in mitigating harmonics and improving the power quality of an electrical system.

Figure 4: Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)

Figure 4 present Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) which is a measure of the harmonic content present in a signal compared to its fundamental frequency.

Table 1: Result Comparison

Sr No.	Parameters	Previous Work	Present Work
1	Technique	ANN	ANFIS
2	Voltage	200V	500V
3	Current	Not Mentioned	10A
4	THD	3.59%	0.15%

Figure 5: THD Comparison

The figure 5 shows the graphical representation of the total harmonic distortion value of the previous and the proposed work.

IV. CONCLUSION

For the purpose of asymmetric selective harmonic current mitigation PWM in active power filters, the Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems (ANFIS) are presented in this study. The simulation is carried out with the assistance of the MATLAB programs. While the previous work was based on artificial neural networks (ANN), the findings of the simulation reveal that the suggested work is based on adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFIS). In the work that is being presented, the overall harmonic distortion has been optimized to be 0.15%, while in the work that came before it was 3.59%. By the work that was suggested, the voltage that was attained was 500V, and the current value that was optimized was 10A, while the previous value was 200V. As a result, the work that has been suggested is much superior to the work that has been done in the past in terms of the approach that was used and the performance of the parameters that were computed.

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